

Postcolonial Trends Of Decolonising The Religious Education Curriculum In Zimbabwe And South Africa

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 15, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: December 09, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Colonial System, Religious Education, South Africa, Christianity</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4313000</p>	<p><i>The colonial system in southern Africa invested in Religious Education (RE) for a long time that post-independent governments took long to change the curriculum. Struggles in South Africa like #FeesMustFall, #RhodesMustFall and #TollFeesMustFall are indications of an overdue conversation. How can RE curricula change respond to this situation because Christianity dominates the sub-region since the missionary-times, Islam is the biggest assertive minority religion, and both demonise Indigenous African Religions (IARs)? Christianity was critical for the success of colonialism in Zimbabwe and South Africa, and must respond to epistemic violence through institutional reframing, rethinking and reconstruction to meet contemporary demands (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2018). Post-independent curricula have been willing to incorporate developing contexts, but planners, who are products of the colonial system, duplicated it from their past. Decolonising the RE curriculum requires a renewed will and affection to deal, radically and accountably, with colonial statues that continuously obstruct academic freedom.</i></p>

1. Introduction

Recent increase in student protests to challenge symbols and statues of coloniality, canons of knowledge, racial identities and epistemological hierarchies in Southern African tertiary institutions has awakened us to the discourse of decolonizing the curriculum (Shay 2016; Le Grange 2016; Chaudhuri, 2016). The decolonizing discourse questions the messages and voices presented by 'canons of knowledge' in the education sector. It puts back the theory of race and identity on the agenda, situating it within the historical, theoretical, epistemological, existential, methodological and contemporary discourses of postcolonial education. This discourse is an alternative to, and critique of, traditional approaches to teaching and learning that emphasise use of abstract paradigms developed for European (western) white-men's capitalist interests. Race politics has been blamed for perpetuating white culture and identity in centres of learning; so this article examines the topic from the prevailing dominant conceptions of race relations in the education sector. In South Africa, a critical engagement with race theory is justified because of the long history of institutionalized white supremacy and privilege that continues to deny the critical voices and experiences of black students and lecturers (Modiri, 2012:405-438). The trends of decolonizing the curriculum thus begin with theoretical and conceptual discussions that inform equality and freedom in the public discourse. The article is interested in how religion has been manipulated, and how change in the curriculum can lead to social change, even though this study will not be able to pursue it to that level. It problematises tensions and contradictions that characterize southern Africa in terms of violence, rape, suicide, moral decay, poverty, femicide, unemployment, human rights and neglect by a highly Christianised region, where some countries like Zimbabwe have as high as 85% of the population professed to be Christian (*Inter-Censal Demography Survey Report*, 2017; Charles, 2019:5). Embedded historical ideologies of race that perpetuate self-hate have been noted as having been advanced by religion during the colonial era that created levels of development according to race, with the white race benefiting the most and the black race the least. The Darwinian theory of evolution that was interwoven into the patriarchal-heterosexual and neoliberal-capitalist class relations in post-apartheid South Africa was used to regard black Africans as a developing race still at its formative stages (Hussain, 2019; Shay, 2016; Heleta, 2016). Due to this, the persistence of the colonialism and racism in education needs to be interrogated in the broader discussion on curriculum change in southern Africa. Current debates on merit, inclusion, diversity, plurality and collegiality. Diversifying voices in curriculum and teaching plan on merited inclusion, can address lack of visibility of plural voices, especially collegial voices, to attain academic freedom (Charles, 2019). This article is broadly concerned about the significance of interdisciplinary thinking that must be engaged, and discovery of the critical voice, in pursuing trends of decolonizing the RE curriculum in a way that might disclose possibilities of racial justice and equality in the educational sector. This article briefly discusses the historical trends and contexts of the RE Curriculum in Southern Africa, and how African learners are playing their part in the process. The study deeply follows trends in Zimbabwe and South Africa but refers to examples in other places in Africa.

Background and Context of the Study

The term “*decolonizing the curriculum*” is of high currency among South African students and lecturers, and this demands that a brief history and context of the South African RE curriculum be discussed to situate the relevance of the term for the study. Younger students have often than not, come to school to assimilate ‘canons’ that are presented by superiors so they can progress in their careers. Decolonizing the curriculum emphasizes the reinvigoration of what, how, where and when something must be taught, and this must be built on the voices and experiences of the marginalized. The endeavour, “with its quest for non-Eurocentric paradigms” (Charles, 2019:2), began in 2011 with the Malaysian Conference on higher education (Alvares and Faruqi, 2012). To decolonise means “creating spaces and resources for a dialogue among all members of the university on how to imagine and envision all cultures and knowledge systems in the curriculum, and with respect to what is being taught and how it frames the world” (Charles, 2019:2). During the colonial era, RE curricula were Eurocentric, Bibliocentric and Christocentric, with, as its major aims, the proselyting of students into followers of the Christian religion. No spaces were created, or resources considered, for dialogue. No African converts participated in framing their religious worlds as their traditional ways of imagination and vision did not make much sense to a writing culture. The syllabus therefore was developed by missionaries for confessional purposes, who underplayed the significance of other religions, including Indigenous African Religion(s) (IARs). There was therefore no official syllabus for missionaries who shaped the curricula to indoctrinate learners with their religious beliefs. At post-independence, *consultative conferences* were carried out in some countries to align curricula and syllabuses along student needs. Unfortunately the curricula carried with it the vestiges of the colonial era and failed to meet the required levels of diversity in a real classroom setting. The teaching and learning of RE was religious indoctrination, which mis-educated the diverse population contexts of people in southern Africa (Maposa, 2014:76). The curriculum to-date has not moved from missionary concepts of RE, hence the need to decolonize the RE curriculum.

On defining curriculum, Charles (2019:3) quoting from Open University, *The Innovating Pedagogy* says,

A curriculum provides a way of identifying the knowledge we value. It structures the ways in which we are taught to think and talk about the world. As education has become increasingly global, communities have challenged the widespread assumption that the most valuable knowledge and the most valuable ways of teaching and learning come from a single European tradition. Decolonizing learning prompts us to consider everything we study from new perspectives. It draws attention to how often the only world view presented to learners is male, white, and European. This isn’t simply about removing some content from the curriculum and replacing it with new content – it’s about considering multiple perspectives and making space to think carefully about what we value. Decolonizing learning helps us to recognize, understand, and challenge the ways in which our world is shaped by colonialism. It also prompts us to examine our professional practices. It is an approach that includes indigenous knowledge and ways of learning, enabling students to explore themselves and their values and to define success on their own terms.

Southern Africa, in which South Africa and Zimbabwe is situated comprise of 11 countries which include Mozambique, Malawi, Zambia, Angola, Namibia, Botswana, Lesotho, Eswatini and Madagascar, with an estimated total population of 345 million people (<https://www.sadc.int/about-sadc/overview/sadc-facts-figures/>). The study will not follow trends in each of the 11 countries in this short space, but it can be assumed that the missionary behaviour followed similar patterns, decolonization in the other countries is implied in this study. The region received British, German, Dutch and Portuguese colonial powers. Each of these colonial powers, including non-colonizing western countries like New Zealand, Australia, Greece, Italy and the United States settled and introduced religious systems that advanced their interests in Christianity, colonialism, and commercialization. Decolonizing the curriculum in the region means interrogating all the vestiges of the former colonizers and emigrants. The reality of religious diversity, because of diverse colonial powers and emigrants is a given, which demands that Southern Africa embrace a multi-faith approach to accommodate the “history of colonisation, internal and international migration, missionary activities, intermarriages, industrialization and technological developments” (Museka, 2012:25; Matemba & Addai-Mununkum, 2017:155). “If education is to do with the development of a child’s autonomy and consequently, if the child is to have genuine religious choice, then the child must be exposed to a multi-faith approach” (Phillips-Bell, 1983:88-89). Unfortunately, the colonizing powers were themselves not in agreement, and most of the educational programmes they introduced were experimental, and were meant to serve their individual and corporate interests. Southern Africa also received an influx of Chinese and Indian personnel who have decided to take permanent abode there. This has brought in a huge influx of cultures and practices that lived under a mono-religious education curriculum.

Unfortunately southern African ethical and moral developments have been disintegrating since the fall of colonialism due to this un-questioned diversity that remained dominated by Christian conversations.

When Colonialism finally fell in the last African country in the early 1990s, it did not go away with Christianity and Commercialization, the other two wings of the colonizing project. Through Christianity and Commercialization, RE continued to perpetuate colonial missionary religion, which reached back into the excesses of Colonialism, making the call for the decolonization of the RE curriculum a worthwhile enterprise. Colonialism is an insidious system that permeated religion, business, political administration and herein education, that post-independent governments set in a system that dictated to them what, how and why things were to be done. This system has been rightly described as a neo-liberal capitalist system. Students' reaction to the way universities are being run happened in Zimbabwe earlier (Hwamiand Kapoor, 2012:31-66), and currently happening in South Africa and the United Kingdom, mostly pioneered by students and staff of an African race. Protests demand serious transformation that corrects a colonial anomaly to accommodate the formerly oppressed black majority. Removal of oppressive systems of education demand replacement of the same with pedagogical forms of education that are democratic and accommodative. A motivated studentship in Zimbabwe was the beginning point in opening the discourse, where it was associated with tremendous enrolments in the form of universal education (Zvobgo, 1999:114). The total condemnation and denial of a white curriculum can be feared to be bending towards reverse racism against the contribution of white culture to the education curriculum (Hussain, 2019). All the same, most Southern Africa countries have begun to draw up constitutive RE curricula to embrace the realities of western-Abrahmic, African, Asiatic and contemporary movements (NRMs). Even national constitutional amendments and referenda are taking this diversity seriously because of emerging varied religious, cultural, scientific and technological advancements from Semitic, Asiatic, African, European, Arabic and American faiths (Museka, 2012:25). Decolonizing the RE curricula is important because religion is found in culture, education, technology and the people's ways of life, which carries the identity and dignity of the human person, and hence cannot be meaningfully assisted by epistemologically Eurocentric, Bibliocentric and Christocentric mono-religious approaches (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2018). Making proselytes through the RE curricula was a colonial project that continued to be exercised in public and private institutions of basic and tertiary learning after the official fall of colonialism. This has undermined/underplayed the cultural developments of indigenous people, demanding for the reconstitution and reconstruction of a relevant and representative religious studies syllabus in a postmodern society (Cotter & Robertson, 2016).

Proponents for curricula transformation argue that there are contextually relevant ways of knowing and being in the post-colonial era to allow the interaction of students, academics and professionals with systems and processes of basic and higher learning institutions in new and better ways. Decoloniality is a thinking that arises from this context, with the view that there are alternative ways of knowing, being and doing ruled by interplays of power and spirituality (Le Grange, 2016). It informs us about how we should interact in contested relationships. Interestingly, education and learning is not an exclusive western cultural product because it has been in Africa for many centuries (see Mali, Egypt, Cush and Timbuktu) (Marah, 2012:143-171), just like it has been in India and China before Europeans became civilized, meaning that no culture can claim to have a preserve of knowledge or its containment more than others (Zawada, 2020). It served host states in many ways, to administer the distribution of resources, justice and security for the people. Similarly, colonial education was designed to serve the interests of colonial state; hence in discussing the element of decolonizing the RE curriculum in southern Africa, similar questions have been asked, especially on the purpose of the RE curriculum. Actually, the processes of education have been shrouded in elements of religiosity, where the Church, State and School lived in contested relationships; hence service of these subjects to humanity led them to be regarded as *Humanities*.

Education at any time is supposed to be used to speak truth to power; but black education during the colonial era was introduced to provide new skilling, knowledge, beliefs and attitudes for their service to the new capitalist ventures. This type of education was formal, and used written books, and hence was "The highly institutionalised, chronologically graded and hierarchically structured 'education' spanning [from] lower primary school [to] the upper reaches of the university" (Coombs and Manzoo, 1974:8). Colonial education lost its importance of standing close to those who cannot represent themselves to the colonizing empire (power), for most often the educationists became part and parcel of the imperial system as they began to 'dine and wine' with the systems and processes of oppression to be accorded the middle class status, thereby ignoring and forgetting the masses they were supposed to represent. Decolonizing the curriculum, and especially the RE curricula, attempts to produce a relevant and inclusive syllabus that embraces the religious and cultural diversity found in the contemporary classroom setting (Museka, 2012).

Research Problem and justification

RE curriculum in Southern Africa, and specifically in Zimbabwe and South Africa, remained colonised, offering missionary RE syllabi decades after the demise of colonialism and several years after the departure of the last missionary, in Zimbabwe for instance. Zimbabwe and South Africa have been affected by high levels of crime and immorality that governments are calling upon religious institutions to instil moral uprightness into the nations (MOPSE, 2015). The two countries have many commonalities including the influence of the British of which Rhodes is a very significant figure on colonisation in both countries. Southern Africa being the last region to be liberated from colonial rule (Zimbabwe, 1980 and South Africa, 1990), and South Africa was the first to be colonised (1652 and Zimbabwe, 1890). The colonial governments invested heavily in the education sector over this length of period and these systems had rooted themselves into the regional governing systems in education, politics, commerce, sport, health, law and social relations. This has made southern Africa a significant region to study on this developing phenomenon. This article explores how the colonial system that permeated every sphere of life can be addressed to allow the educational triad, the teacher, the learner and the content (Curriculum) meaningful space to change in the unfolding social, historical, political, religious and educational context. Change of curriculum has implications for each of the three elements of the written and unwritten curriculum if the desired outcomes can be achieved. The question to ask is: What trends are taking place to put dominant Christianity in dialogue with assertive Islam and the demonised Indigenous African Religions (IARs)? How is the discourse of curriculum change taking place in Zimbabwe and South Africa? How can RE respond to the unfolding situation dominated by reactions to former curricula developments?

The theory of decolonising the Curriculum

Decolonising the curriculum refers to the conversation that imagines and envisions educational content (what is taught) and method (how it is taught) interact in cultural and knowledge systems and frames. The curriculum being decolonised was established at a time the region was dependent on colonial systems. To decolonise is to consider sources to be given priority and options for establishing content and methods of education. A decolonised curriculum in Africa is usually rooted in a context, the African context, in order to empower Africans restore their cultural knowledge systems and to support indigenous epistemological pedagogies. Attitudinal changes should begin by treating Africans, especially black learners, as agents of radical change rather than a 'problem' (Fielding, 2001:123-141). It dismantles all forms of implicit and explicit colonialist powers and cultural forces that prevented political and institutional diversity in basic and tertiary education in the region. It can be referred to a structural interruption of hegemonic forms of knowledge that were produced and continue to be reproduced by RE departments trapped in Eurocentric knowledge formations. This article interrogates the concept of decolonising the curriculum in political and religious history as well as educational context. From here, interrogate the colonial RE curriculum before we can look at aspects to be considered in curriculum change.

Interrogating the Colonial Religious Curriculum

The colonial religious education system supported the separation of African and western development, hence religious education anointed the Apartheid system in South Africa and colonialism in Zimbabwe. This was influenced by capitalism, globalism, technology, and secularism, making colonial thinking an insidious epistemological framework in all processes of the education system (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2018). As a tool of colonization, it systematically and compulsorily arranged school subjects to be taught to learners at primary, secondary and tertiary levels, which reduced choice, innovation and entrepreneurship. However, informal education has no structure, and it is "the life long process by which every person acquires and accumulates knowledge, skills, attitudes and insights from daily experiences and exposure to the environment at home, at work, at play; from the examples and attitudes of family and friends; from travel, reading newspapers and books; or listening to the radio or viewing films or television" (Coombs and Manzoo, 1974:8). This established "a hierarchy of philosophies that places western civilization as a universal benchmark for progressive thought" (Kanetkar, 2019). The unintended and unplanned new emergence of Christian spirituality to engage in fighting the separation between western and African epistemologies through an attribution of the religious voice to the vestiges of the colonial system unexpectedly came out to broaden the horizons, and to widen the scope for more diversity of thought and culture (Kanetkar, 2019; Zawada, 2020). The same education that was acquired under colonialism arose to challenge the system that gave birth to it. Thus the fight against the Apartheid system of development began during the colonial era, with a few voices, which are early signs of the decolonization of the RE curriculum for the Christian faith. The Church believes in the Spirit, its voice is prophetic and, it provides advocacy to the weak, poor, downtrodden and sick. Hence, the new call for the decolonization of the curriculum is a spiritualization of the voice of the prophets to realize the place of the Church in the lives of its people. Mashau & Kgate (2019) say that this spiritualisation was lost at some point, and the decolonizing project is a revival of the voice that was silenced after independence, or was sent to the intensive care unit (ICU), paralyzed, captured, neutralized or unauthorized. The voice cannot be ignored as more and more Africans have become educated and are demanding change. Derrida says: "To ask such questions, such difficult questions,

requires that we change the most resistant, archaic structures of our desire” (1999:27) happens when we begin to critique our own past.

Many happenings indicate that the voice of the Church is being mocked by greedy politicians who cannot attend to corruption and gender-based violence like the populous abuse case of Nigerian neo-Pentecostal in South Africa, pastor Timothy Omotoso, who was accused of child/women abuse and the commercialization of the gospel (Ramatswana, 2015). The demands on curriculum change are based on the view that RE cannot continue business as usual because its epistemologies are not alive and responsive to the realities of African people living and working at the margins (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2018). It is a ‘dead’ faith with no practical results (James 1:27). Curricula change are efforts to flip tables, keep doors open, and engage further with the present in view of the past (Shay, 2016). The examples of some African liberationists like Thomas Sankara taught in universities influence students’ reactions to difficulties in the academia, as they embrace the Sankaran ‘hermeneutic of madness’. This hermeneutic was practiced by Jesus when he faced the spiritual badness of the Jewish leaders – he turned tables, but did not close temple doors (Mashau & Kgatle, 2019; Heleta, 2016). In an interview with Swiss journalist Jean-Philippe Rapp in 1985, Thomas Sankara was reportedly heard saying:

You cannot carry out fundamental change without a certain amount of madness. In this case, it comes from nonconformity, the courage to turn your back on the old formulas, the courage to invent the future. It took the mad men of yesterday for us to be able to act with extreme clarity today. I want to be one of those mad men. ... We must dare to invent the future.

In Africa, Thomas Sankara was right: ‘If we need change and see change, we must be mad’.

This is supported by the second one, the ‘hermeneutic of naked truth’. In Africa, people are very economical on the truth; they are not happy to face the demons of truth (Mashau & Kgatle, 2019). Africans so much endear relationships that they evade the truth to help a disorderly to keep a face. Among the Shona, it called “*Kudya uroyi nokusvoda*” (Facing one’s fate for fear of shame). If change must be enjoyed, the truth must be told.

Further, curriculum change generates and enables study programmesto be useful for addressing dissonance between theory and practice. Education is revolutionary and not neutral that it allows young people to obtain the intricacies of life such as marriage, life pensions, jobs, and insurances. It provides a new narrative for hopeless young people (Mashau & Kgatle, 2019). Unfortunately, the gospel is being traded for money. The commercialization of the gospel has relegated morality for money. For instance, homosexuality in most African countries is regarded as the betrayal of sexuality; and so are a number of human personhood being traded by religious leaders for money (Sadgrove, et al. 2012:103-129). In Zimbabwe and South Africa, such religious leaders are regarded as teachers of immorality because they betray morality and spirituality for money and power. They use ‘soft’ theology to profile the poor and needy without preparing for serious skirmishes found in ‘hard’ theology by standing up for the voice of the people. The process needs to begin in the Church, addressing its own abuses of women, children, immigrants and the downtrodden, because the marriage between colonialism and Christianity drowned that voice. Post-colonial prophets’ voces have been killed because they are also married to this dispensation. The institutionalised Church chose temporal gains of power, and neglected its charisma to liberate the downtrodden, widow, orphan, poor and needy (Boff, 2012). Its fate began when its prophets started dining with politicians, capitalists (corrupt billionaires and governments) who perpetuate slave mentality through self-hate (Methula, 2017). Gathogo (2008), a Kenyan PhD graduate of the University of KwaZulu Natal argues about use of African philosophy, concept so hospitality need to confront human tensions, race and identity issues, and social violence in Southern Africa. Self-hate, which is an internalized hatred of a person of the same people-group, is a time bomb for Southern Africa as exhibited by sporadic xenophobic and Afrophobic attacks that are taking advantage of vulnerable nationalities and genders. Gathongo (2008) argues that Africans are generally ‘hospitable people’, and especially to foreigners, until such visitors start to behave in ways they believe undermine the sovereignty of their society. Social ills in southern African are therefore easy to address if self-hate is dealt away with, and people become mentally liberated.

In a theological conference for Church leaders at the University of South Africa entitled: “Towards Prophetic and Contextual Relevant Theological Training in post-Apartheid South Africa (22-23 October 2019)” the College of Human Sciences introduced a new degree on contextually relevant theological education to recover the church’s prophetic voice in the world. It was emphasized that for it to succeed, local people need to be part of the process, because most development projects in African countries do not involve local people. Ideas are generated at the top and fed to the people by the elites. Rulers and capitalists, often than not, have colluded in defrauding masses. The practice was developed by colonialism leaders, wherein African communities were not involved at both ideological and practical levels, in policy-making and implementation. Europeans however, were consulted for the drawing up of every policy as well as its implementation. It can be correctly argued that

the current RE curricula, when it was first drawn up, missionaries consulted with local and overseas missionary boards on the content, concept and context of RE instruction. They participated in drawing up curricula that serve their colonial, Christian and commercial interests. Theology was very important for achieving racial harmony, law and order in colonised nations. Unfortunately, it was not designed for post-colonial Africa, thence the 2019 UNISA conference on curricula change. African communities urgently need to be involved in seeing and learning; teaching and researching; learning with communities; and in teaching on policy-making, confronting government and capitalist interests. Involvement of communities reduces the tendency of drafters colluding with capitalists and rulers to draw up a curriculum that serves their interests. On collusion, one UNISA panelist argued: ‘We have realized that dining and wining with Caesar in the evening and criticizing him in the morning is very difficult’. This brings us to demand the shift for justice to all in African communities because the critical ideology of Apartheid that captured the Church gave a blessing to oppression; and silenced all forms of transformation by sanctioning colonial injustice (Mashau & Kgate, 2019). These disabling canons of colonialism were taught in educational centres and created dissonance in the minds and hearts of graduates who instead assisted in perpetuating the oppression. Decolonizing the RE curriculum here reinvigorates the religious image, especially God’s voice among falsehoods, which is ‘good orthopraxy’. It exposes ‘dead orthodoxy’ expressed in heresy, untruthfulness and neglect of the needy (De Vries, 1978). This forces us to examine the perspectives of a decolonized RE curriculum.

Perspectives of a Decolonised RE Curriculum

The conception of decolonization presented above raises the thinking that it is an imagination and vision of what and how RE must be taught in the schools. This refers to a curriculum that was drawn up by the colonizers to serve their own interests, and when the countries attained independence, the colonial thinking in the system was not removed and replaced by African knowledges and methods of education. A decolonized RE curriculum embraces indigenous epistemological pedagogies, which is necessary for the transformation of Africa and the Africans. In decolonizing the curriculum, it is not assumed that all elements of the current curriculum are going to be removed, but that new attitudes, agents, content, methods and contexts are going to be imbedded into the existing structures and institutions to interrupt inherited forms of knowledge and power in political administration, religious history and educational context that continues to reproduce their past. As Bozatelek (2011:469-484) suggests, decolonizing the curriculum needs to acknowledge difference, accept the past and learn from it, and participate in designing new epistemological techniques relevant to the new context.

Firstly, in decolonizing the RE curriculum, especially in Christianity, it has to begin with the concept of God. Southern Africa, predominantly Christian, has the highest crime rates in Africa (like murders, rape cases, and femicide) not because there are more non-believers there, but because they have a wrong concept of God. Africans were told that they were made in the image and likeness of God; but not true genetic identity of the creator. The Bible taught that all of humanity was of the same flesh and blood but some missionaries behaved as if they were genetically begotten of God in how they treated blacks. Good missionaries lived differently. Reginald Garfield Todd and Jean Grace Todd took African citizenship, and John White and Arthur Shearly Cripps, are classified also as ‘white heroes’ (Chigwedere, 2017). They neither behaved like gods, nor as if God was created from their images. However, the collective consciousness of the white men’s God says that God is male, white and absent; probably in a mine or forest somewhere looking for a fortune. This behaviour taught Africans that Europeans lived as if God was created in the image of humankind. In fact, a male white God incorporates western rather than African patriarchy. The father who is absent on errands or at work, has influenced modern families to have increased rates of divorce with families run by single mothers and no fathers, and ‘we’ are now living in the precepts of an absentee father. This makes God a father biased towards men and whites while he lives in Heaven. The iconography of a God who is remote, a man and white makes God a judgmental father (Macdonald, 2016). Children on earth are instructed through an electronic remote-control in terms of behaviour and morality. This judgmental God is not a bringer of freedom and liberation but a perpetuator of colonial oppression. Regrettably, the God ‘who derives pleasure from burning people in hell’ is also violent and bloodthirsty. Thus the followers of this God condemn all other religions except their own; hence followers of this God’s religion are sectarian like their father. This situation contrasts with what the founder of the religion taught, Jesus Christ, who taught about the application of the concept of love. which Jesus, taking from the prophets, taught his followers to love God, their-selves and others (Deut 6:4-4; Matt. 22:27, 37). Jesus teaches that love is the character; image and correct concept of Godhood, in whose image humanity was created. Colonizers had a wrong concept of God, and of themselves, hence they treated Africans, on the basis of the wrong concept of others. The concept became internalized by Africans who hated so much white oppression that they were schooled to exercise the same oppression on their African compatriots. Like in *The White Image in the Black Mind* (2000) M. Bay argues that the long history of black subjugation and mental colonization need to be desegregated to remove white ethnography in black minds, if Africans can become fully liberated. In South Africa they suggested to do this by firstly removing white icons on church walls and

replacing them with black icons because Jesus was not white. The movement for the black Jesus was born out of this context, because colour mattered in the colonizing project hence it is relevant in 'our' decolonizing concept of God (Boswell, 1998:161-195).

The material blackness of Jesus possibly blended him with Africans while hiding in Egypt from bloodthirsty whites at home (Macdonald, 2016). Use of African spirituality to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) quickens progress, especially on gender equality. Africans do not have gender pronouns for God, because God is gender-neutral. Acceptance of women can begin from this contextual image of God to accept women in male reserved jobs. Africa also has urgent metaphysical issues. This calls for the *metaphysical interpretation* of the gospel. *Metaphysical* issues have changed constitutions and led to revolutions, especially perpetuated by student demonstrations (Macdonald, 2016). In South Africa, they were sparked by high costs of education and transport students can no longer afford due to the persistent worship of colonialism in post-Apartheid South Africa (Shay 2016; Le Grange 2016; Chaudhuri, 2016). In a decolonized curriculum, all contexts and experiences of Africans are fully incorporated, inclusive of metaphysical needs for black children with absentee fathers.

In southern Africa, there is a tendency by people of engaging in physical violence, destruction of property and taking of human life to register grievances. Violent behaviour, including loss of human life, was inherited from Colonialism, which reveals a radical loss of unity in the human body and mind. However, religion has (a duty) to come out of its confinements and address social 'rot' in lives of individuals, families and communities. The central objective of religion is to worship God through preaching and discipleship meant to help the people of God live a moral life; also called 'functional ecclesiology'. Moral regeneration is the duty of all religious institutions because their teachings look beyond the grave, where present moralities influence eternal outcomes. John Calvin (10th July 1509 – 27th May 1564) taught about the regeneration of God, where one had to remove his/her eye glasses to properly understand who God is and what God is doing in the world or how God engages in changing the world so they can take part in the change. The worshipping community embodies and sustains a lifestyle of change - it generates moral change, and restores the lost unity of body and mind. In Zimbabwe and South Africa, reports of dysfunctional children abound today although there were rare cases of multiple sclerosis at independence (Dean, et al. 1994:1064-1069). The region is dominated by Christianity, meaning the religion failed to live out for its confessional goals. With absentee parents, children brought to institutions are abused and raped by foster parents from the same religious institution and community to further hurt the needy rather than heal them. Curriculum change is therefore an urgent matter to restore mental and physical health, moral uprightness, social inclusivity and civil tolerance because the region has a ticking bomb of unemployment, violence, moral decay, poverty, femicide, suicide and the labeled boy child. Democracy never bothered itself with important matters of human development as it quickly came up with easy answers to ideological questions by changing unregistered beer gardens into taverns to endlessly entertain the jobless. Euphemisms ridiculed religion such as 'Give us the bottle and the Bible; or the pint and the preacher'. Less meaningful transformation have seen the waning political power of colonialism, but has failed to see the birth of true democracy that was given. Colonialism was and is insidiously permeated into all institutions of society that democracy has failed to take genuine roots on the soil (Mamdani, 2001:651-664).. Those who participated in the struggle have continued 'to return from the war, alive or in coffins', nations remain stuck in those justifications, and nations rotate in the same positions because *mafikezolo* (newcomers) cannot establish institutions to fulfill the goals of the struggle they did not enter.

Further, reviewers of the RE curriculum have to consider that a study of religion in classroom settings live for both its theoretical discourse and dominant functional ecclesiology. Religion is first a confession of faith, and has a mandate to spread the intentions of God for the world. The church went onto the streets in demand for freedom from colonizers because of this drive. The Church is a religious organization that has a vision, mission, values and strategies to fulfill when its leaders and members are engaged in contextual priorities that can transform its systems. The continuous connection of religion with the people's situations helps to give the organization an imaginative function. Re-imagination is a continuous process that continues to restructure itself, to remain relevant, dynamic, relational, time bound and to create a safe place for everyone. The structure silences the cries of people, hence when a religious institution re-imagines itself, restructures itself, prioritises the context and imagines from the ground; it allows those who enter it to get into it to help transform its teachings and reshape its structures in a way that will silence people's cries. Unfortunately, functional ecclesiology in the Church has been reduced to systems of fundraising, entrepreneurship and entertainment, rather than be an agent of change wherever it finds itself (Mashau & Kgatle, 2019). The church in South Africa is being regarded like a *stockvel* (system of raising money), *business* (place to enrich the prophet) and *theatre* (place to entertain people), hence there is need to decolonize the RE Curriculum from commercialization and commoditization of the gospel by uncouthly religious priests (Methula, 2017).

Further, a review of the RE curriculum needs to consider the relevance of being prophetic in a context, as Paul Tillich (20th August 1886 – 22th October 1965) believes that God is inexhaustible, and empowers people, so ‘what happens in the world is representative of what happens in the worship centre’. In the Bible, Jeremiah was asked to leave the Temple and to go to the Potter’s House (Jeremiah 18:1-11). What Paul Tillich says and what Jeremiah was asked to do, speak volumes about God’s concern for justice, revealed in Deuteronomy and used by Old Testament, New Testament and contemporary Prophets of morality like Paul Tillich. Prophets revealed that God does not desire sacrifices and offerings at the altar (worship in sacred places) but justice and mercy (1 Samuel 9:22-23). This is a call, in the economics and politics of the Church, to shelter abused women and children and to protect survivors of church violators. The Church is today shamed by the behaviour of some institutions like the Catholic Church, whose priests, have been arrayed as playing God by oppressing the dignity, identity and justice of abused children without taking disciplinary procedures on perpetrators. In *Sex, priests, and secret codes*, Doyle, Sipe and Wall (2006) argue that the Catholic Church has a 2000-year paper trail of sexual abuse; the reason why Pope Francis has been challenged to restructure the Catholic Church on the abuse of every member in the face of patriarchy in that Church. This hopes to transform Christianity from perpetuating social oppression like femicide by toxic masculinities that treat women as ‘spare ribs good for the brie’; but to restore healing and dignity to bruised, burned and battered women through true justice and mercy (Hadebe, 2016).

Further, song and dance is the heartbeat of African identity and authenticity. RE Curriculum reviewers need to appreciate that political activism in Africa was driven by song and dance more than it was driven by rational arguments. In Zimbabwe, *pungwes* (overnight meetings) were done through music (radio), song and dance to drive people’s consciousness towards the war (Matiza, 2015:62-73). In South Africa, Steve Biko’s *Black Consciousness Movement* was probably James Cone’s Baptist Black Theology in the United States of America that was borrowed and adopted in South Africa’s struggle for independence (Biko, 1970). Biko saw people’s daily lived activity and the education of followers conveyed through song and dance. In fact, Africans live, die, walk, sleep, eat and drink music, and in fact the black God of Africans, likes music and dance to convey messages to the live during that authentic moment (Pityana, 2008). At a traditional ceremony the writer attended, spirit mediums became possessed when the rhythm of the song, dance and drum were at their tensest moments. Such songs can be conflated between politics and religion, and can be effectively used to convey messages to the new context. Songs are a testimony and conviction to an act. They were sung at work, especially by people making railway lines in forced labour, like the popular *Shosholozo* song (Levine, 2005), hence they contained the spirituality of the marketplace, hence use of such songs makes religion identify and suffer with the people. This article implores that RE curricula review that is fully decolonized should consider how music and dance become a full part of the African RE Curricula.

Above and beyond song and dance, the RE curriculum review needs to consider the use of the media to shape the content and context of religious influence on learners. Several media platforms that have been used and have disseminated information and projected themselves can indicate to us how religious appearances have dominated airwaves in the past decades. The RE curriculum cannot ignore use of the internet to make groups access religious materials. Mass media is part and parcel of the RE curriculum as it speaks to millions of people at the same time. Media is not a new thing because it was through printing that Christianity became a transformed religion in the 16th century. The evangelism crusades of the late 1900s were made successful by the use of public address systems. In the 3rd industrial revolution, media can be used to convey important religious/spiritual messages to the people. The sacred culture that used to be secretive is driven and exposed to the open market by the media; and it is no longer confined to one part of the day in a week, in some church building for it is now brought into people’s homes. Media thus is important for both secular and sacred purposes.

Conclusion

The article has examined trends of decolonising the RE Curriculum in Southern Africa, a last region to be liberated from colonial rule, and also the first to be occupied for settlement and expansion in Africa. Whites invested heavily in education, which demand curriculum review as numerous protests indicate discontent with exhausted icons and statues of white colonialism there, inclusive of out-of-date materials, methods and concepts used in basic and tertiary education. RE was used pacify African resistance, and has mostly offered a monolithic syllabus to reduce diversities of ideas and moralities. Despite religious diversity in the region, rape, incest, promiscuity [homosexuality], murder, robbery, abortion, suicide and violence have been on the increase. Dismantling Eurocentric thinking in this can build national moral academies that can rethink, reframe and reconstruct compliant institutions for the contemporary multicultural world. Unpacking the concept of God is its first call; addressing capitalist tendencies its second; allowing religion to live for its mission its third;

acknowledging the context its forth; and adopting local forms of success and keeping abreast with contemporary transformations its fifth and last. RE curriculum transformation thus must find ways of holding educational institutions accountable to dismantling statues of epistemic violence that continue to stand in the way of postcolonial freedom and continue to provoke the postcolonial black learner.

Competing interests

The author declares no competing interests.

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